

INVESTIGATION OF SI-GEL-NR INTERACTION IN SI-GEL/NR VULCANIZATE AND THE EFFECT OF PEG ON THE RUBBER VULCANIZED

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1 General Introduction

Natural rubber(NR) was originally derived from latex which has molecular weight in the range of 1 00,000 to 1,000,000. Its properties is normally very stretchy, flexible and extremely waterproof. After vulcanization NR can be used in widen temperature window and can be used in various application. In term of mechanical properties, many types of reinforcements are still needed to improve the properties.

There are many reinforcing materials for NR such as carbon black, silica, fly ash, calcium carbonate, clay and etc. Carbon black and silica are the most popular fillers in natural rubber composites. Precipitated silica(PSi) is generally used as reinforcing filler for light color rubber products and can improve the abrasion resistance of the NR vulcanizates. Nonetheless the use of silica causes many problems such as agglomeration and poor distribution in rubber matrix because of their high polar silanol groups on the surface. When silica is added into rubber at high concentration, it tends to form “filler-filler interaction”. This would cause an increase in compound viscosity and gives rise to flow difficulty during processing. The chemical treatment of silica surface has become the most successful method to increase rubber–filler interaction and reduce filler–filler interaction [1]. There's also the idea of using in-situ formed silica in rubber latex to overcome the poor distribution [2-3]

As Thailand is a country in Southeast Asia where grow a large amount of rice and rice hull is a big bunch of agricultural waste. After burning rice hull to obtain energy for electric industry, rice hull ash is also a large amount of waste. Rice hull ash (RHA) was found to contain over 60% silica and can be used as an economically valuable raw material for the production of silicates and silica [3]. Our previous work [4-5] was trying to enhance the distribution of silica in NR matrix by using the silica that gelled in-situ from sodium silicates solution in the same reactor with the coagulation of NR latex. Where in-situ Silica gel(Si-gel) [1-2] is type of silica that gelled meanwhile NR latex is coagulating. The

rubber will be named Si-gel/NR. The distribution of silica in NR matrix was enhanced. The problem of Si-gel was the high surface area lead to retardation of vulcanization reaction. The main problem of silica in this process was the high surface area lead to retardation of vulcanization reaction.

It was found that glycols were able to be used as an activator in vulcanization reaction. The glycol was found to form a buffer layer on the surface of silica where benefit to reduce the silica–zinc interaction and thus enhance the vulcanization reaction [6-7].

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is a polyether which their molecular mass could be below 20,000 g/mol. PEG is the most being used for an activator in vulcanization reaction because of its low volatility. In general, PEG affects compound properties through the crosslink modification, filler network formation and filler agglomeration [6-7].

Crosslink density can investigate by different torque, swelling measurement and glass transition temperature (T_g) [8-11]. T_g of rubber vulcanizates was obtained from DMA. The increasing of crosslink density is shown high interaction between natural rubber and filler by the increased of T_g .

In this research, we aimed to study the effect of PEG with various molecular weights on cure characteristic, mechanical properties and morphology. Thermal stability of Si-gel/NR composite with addition of PEG will also be investigated. The dispersion of Si-gel in rubber was also aimed to be enhanced. The interaction between NR molecule and silica particles in Si-Gel/NR+PEG and 15PSi/NR+PEG by using DMA is also introduced.

2 Methodology

The research is divided into 2 parts. In the first part, PEG with variation of its molecular weight was studied. The effect of PEG on cure characteristic, mechanical properties of Si-Gel/NR is revealed. The dispersion of Si-gel in the rubber is also examined.

The second part of the research is concentrated on using PEG200 compared with PEG1000 added into Si-gel/NR compound. The cure characteristic of the compounds, mechanical properties and thermal stability will be investigated. The methodology is as followed.

2.1 Chemical

Rubber and curative: Natural rubber latex (60%DRC) was purchased from Resin arts, Bangkok, Thailand. The curative additives were kindly supplied by Reliance Technochem Co., Ltd., Bangkok, Thailand.

Reinforcing Filler: Precipitated silica (PSi) named of ULTRASIL[®] was purchased from Evonik Wellink Silica (Nanping) Fujian, China.

Stabilization Chemical: Igepal CO-890 was purchased from SIGMA-ALDRICH, Inc., Steinheim, Germany.

PEG: PEG was purchased from Merck Schuchardt OHG, Hohenbrunn, Germany.

2.2 Preparation of Rubber filled Silica

1000 g of NR latex (60 % DRC) was diluted to 30 % DRC before stabilized with 3 % w/v Igepal. The stabilized NR latex was then gently stirred with mechanical stirrer for 24 hour. Sodium silicate solution was prepared by extraction 10 grams rice hull ash in 300 ml of 1 M NaOH for 12 hours. Silicate solution was then mixed with stabilized 30 % DRC NR latex to obtain 15 phr of Si-gel with respect to dried rubber. After that the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7 by using 5%v/v H₂SO₄. The mixture was then precipitated with methanol. Precipitated NR was filtered and washed with water for several times until free from H₂SO₄, and then the rubber was dried in an oven at 60 °C until its weight was constant. The rubber will be named Si-gel/NR. The TGA analysis indicated that the silica content was found to be 15 phr with respect to dried NR.

2.3 Rubber compounding and Vulcanization of Rubber Compounds

The dried NR sheet with in-situ Si-gel or PSi was masticated on a two roll mill (CHAREON TUT, Samutprakarn, Thailand) until the banding is formed on the roll, then the following additives was added stepwise: 2 phr of PEG (MW 200, 300 and 400 will be used in the first part, and MW 1000 will be used in the second part of the experiment), 5 phr of ZnO, 3 phr of stearic acid, 0.5 phr of MBT, 0.2 phr of DPG and finally 3 phr of sulphur.

The compound was then mixed thoroughly on the two roll. Cure characteristic properties were investigated using Moving Die Rheometer (MDR, Model GT-M2000, GOTECH Testing Machine, Ind., Taiwan) at 160 °C resulting scorch and cure times, minimum and maximum torques,. The compounds were subsequently compressed in a compression molding machine (CHAREON TUT, Samutprakarn, Thailand) to a 90 % cure, with the hydraulic pressure of 1000 PSI, at 160 °C, with cure time obtained from MDR stated earlier.

2.4 Testing of Rubber Vulcanizates

Tensile properties of the vulcanized rubber composites were monitored in terms of tensile modulus, tensile strength and elongation at break, according to ASTM D412-98a using dumbbell-shaped samples. Tear strength was also evaluated according to ASTM D624-00. These tests were carried out using the universal testing machine (Instron, model 5969, Instron Engineering Corporation, USA) with the testing speed of 500 mm/min.

The morphology of the vulcanizates was also revealed using scanning electron microscope (CamScan MX2000, UK). Swelling of the vulcanizates was carried out in Toluene, at ambient temperature, and calculated using equation 1, where w₁ and w₂ is sample weight before and after immersion into Toluene.

$$\text{swelling ratio} = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w_1} \quad \text{equation 1}$$

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) in tension mode was carried out at a frequency of 1 Hz and dynamic and static stress of 0.1% and 1.0% respectively. A heating rate, 2 °C/min was used. Tg value is taken as the point of deflection of the tan δ curve from the base line.

3. Result and Discussion

Part I

Effect of Molecular weight of PEG on rubber vulcanized

3.1 Cure Characteristic and Physical Properties

The cure characteristic parameters of 15Si-gel/NR+PEG compound comparing with 15PSi/NR+PEG compound obtained from MDR are presented in **Table 1** and were plotted into **Figures 1-3**. As can be seen, scorch time and cure time, in **Figure 1**,

were decreased with the addition of PEG. This is explained by the fact that the hydrogen bonding occurs between $-OH$ of $HO-(CH_2CH_2O)_n-H$ and silanol groups on the silica surface. This results in the formation of a buffer layer, as illustrated in **Figure 4**. This buffer layer can reduce the silica-zinc interaction and subsequently lead to activation of vulcanization reaction. The density of the crosslink in rubber vulcanizates is then increased. The phenomenon is also responsible for the increased in different torque which is showed in **Figure 3**.

Figure 1 Scorch time (ts) and cure time (tc) of NR compounds

Figure 2 Minimum (ML) torque and maximum (MH) torque of NR compounds.

Figure 3 The different torque of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG during testing in MDR.

It was explained elsewhere that the present of Si-gel clusters in 15Si-gel/NR caused the increased in

scorch time and cure time because the porosity of Si-gel was higher than PSi [4,5] and this could absorb accelerator even more amount on its surface than PSi. After the addition of PEG, the absorption of the glycol would act as the buffer layer and then the decreased of scorch time and cure time were found. However, in both fillers systems, the molecular weight of PEG was found to be un-effect on both characteristic times. This could be because of their molecular weights are not much different or their polarities are not much different.

Figure 4 SEM micrograph of Si-gel added with PEG where the buffer layer on silica surface is shown.

It was also found that minimum and maximum torques obtained from MDR were increased with the PEG, **Figure 2**. Considering different torques, in **Figure 3**, it was also showed that the different torques are also increased with the PEG. Generally, the different torques obtained by MDR can be a guide line for crosslink density in the rubber vulcanizates. In our case, it can also be comprehended that crosslink density of the vulcanizates with PEG in both filler systems was increased with the addition of PEG. Also the various molecular weight of PEG added was found to be uneffect on the crosslink density.

3.2 Mechanical Properties of Vulcanizates

As crosslink density of the vulcanizates was increased by the addition of PEG and this resulted in the increased of secant modulus, at 100 and 200 percentage of strain, of the rubber vulcanizate as shown in **Figure 5**. Crosslink density is also responsible for the tensile strength and tear strength of rubber vulcanizates [4, 6], as elucidated in **Figure 6** and **Figure 7** respectively.

Figure 5 Modulus at 100% strain and 200% strain of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 6 The tensile strength of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 7 Tear strength of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Considering swelling ratio of the rubber vulcanizates, as crosslink density of Si-gel/NR is lower than that of PSi/NR hence Si-gel/NR possesses swelling ratio in toluene higher than that of PSi/NR. It can be generally seen that the vulcanizates with PEG result in better toluene resistance than that without PEG as the former system can perform vulcanization reaction better than the latter. However, when the molecular weight of PEG is increased the toluene resistance is slightly decreased. This is due to the decreased polarity of PEG. SEM micrographs, shown in Figure 9, also show the well

dispersion of silica in the NR matrix for both systems.

Figure 8 Swelling ratio of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 9 SEM Micrographs of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

PART II

Effect of PEG 200 and PEG 1000 on rubber compound and rubber vulcanizates

3.3 Cure Characteristic and Mechanical Properties of Si-gel/NR and PSi/NR

This part of the research aims to use PEGs that possess their different state, i.e. liquid and solid form. The cure characteristic of 15Si-gel/NR and 15PSi/NR+PEG compounding with PEG200 and PEG1000 obtained from MDR is shown in **Figure**

10. It was found that the addition of PEG confirmedly decreased both scorch time and cure time as it was found by the others [3-6] and in the previous part. This was responsible by the hydrogen bonding between –OH of PEG and silanol groups on the silica surface as mentioned earlier.

Figure 10 a) Scorch time (ts) and cure time (tc) and (c) different torque (Δ s) of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG during testing in MDR.

It was also shown in **Figure 11** that secant modulus of the rubber vulcanizates were enhanced by the addition of PEG. Nonetheless, the system with PEG1000 was seemed to clearly exhibit less in its modulus. This could be due to the less polarity of the PEG1000 than PEG200 and thus less buffer layer will be formed consequently more absorption of accelerator on the surface of both PSi and Si-gel. The vulcanization reaction was then found to be suffered. This also led to the lesser in tensile strength, shown in **Figure 12**. As dispersion of silica was improved in both systems, elongation at break, shown in **Figure 13**, of the rubber vulcanizates was then found to be progressive. In term of PEG1000, the similarity of their elongation at break was found. This could be due to the lubricating effect is more pronounce than the performing of buffer layer on the

silica surface. This is also suffered the modulus of the rubber vulcanizate (as shown in **Figure 10**).

Figure 11 Modulus at 100% strain of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

The swelling behavior was also decreased with the present of PEG. Due to the lesser polarity of PEG1000 than PEG200, crosslink density of silica/NR filled with PEG1000 is thus slightly less than silica/NR filled with PEG200. This resulted in slightly high in swelling ratio as shown in **Figure 14**.

Figure 12 The tensile strength of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 13 The percentage of elongation at break of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 14 Swelling ratios of NR vulcanizates

Figure 15 SEM Micrographs of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates

It is very clear from SEM micrographs shown in **Figure 14** that addition of PEG200 could enhance better distribution for both Psi and Si-gel in NR, than PEG1000. This is by the reason of less polarity of PEG1000 and thus less interaction between PEG1000 on silica surface could be performed. The aggregation of PSi particles could then be found, as shown in **Figure 14 (f)**. Meanwhile there was no sign of aggregation of Si-gel particles in NR matrix.

3.4 Thermal Aging of Rubber Vulcanizates

Mechanical properties before and after thermal aging of NR vulcanized were plotted into **Figure 16 (a)-(c)**. The changes in mechanical properties of

vulcanizate was calculated using equation 2 and the result is presented in **Figure 17**. Considering **Figure 17 (a)**, it can be seen that having PEG in the vulcanizates, the decrement of modulus at 100% strain was less than that without PEG. This is because of the crosslink that was increased by the present of PEG. The increase in crosslink density in the rubber vulcanizate also resulted in the enhancement in tensile strength as shown in **Figure 16 (b)**. However, elongation at break of the Psi/NR+PEG and Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates compared with Psi/NR and Si-gel/NR vulcanizates, the result, in **Figure 16 (c)** showed similar percentage of elongation. As mentioned earlier that PEG can act not only as formation of buffer layer on silica surface but also as lubricating agent, this therefore compensate the elongation at break of the vulcanizate.

$$P = \left[\frac{(A - O)}{O} \right] \times 100 \quad \text{equation 2}$$

Comparing the effect of PEG200 and PEG1000 on thermal ageing of silica filled rubber vulcanizate, it was shown in the result that the mechanical properties of vulcanizates with PEG1000 was slightly more sensitive to heat than that with PEG200. This could be due to the less polarity of PEG1000 and hence producing linkage with more sulfur. The lubricating agent of PEG1000 onto rubber was also more effective than PEG200.

It is also noticeable that the rubber vulcanizate filled with Si-gel also show ageing by heat treatment more than the other case. This could be explained by the high porosity of Si-gel than that of PSi. The high porosity of Si-gel was confirmed by nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms, pore-size distributions in **Figure 18 (a)-(b)**. The high porosity of Si-gel led to high absorption of accelerator on its surface hence the crosslink type was thought to be more with polysulfide linkages. These polysulfide linkages are very sensitive to heat compare with di and mono sulfide linkages. Thus the percentage change in Si-gel/NR+PEG was found slightly higher than that of PSi/NR+PEG.

Figure 16 (a) Modulus at 100% strain (b) tensile strength (c) percentage of elongation at break of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 17 The percentage change in (a) modulus at 100%strain (b) tensile strength (c) %elongation at break of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 18 (a) Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms of Si-gel and PSi (b) The BET surface area of Si-gel and PSi

3.5 Dynamic mechanical properties of NR vulcanizates

The addition of PEG is being the cause of the increased in crosslink density, as explained in the previous sections and this can be confirmed by DMA results. The storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and tan delta are presented in **Figure 19-21** respectively. T_g of the NR vulcanizates obtained from $\text{Tan}\delta$ is presented in **Figure 22**.

It is exhibited in **Figure 19** that the incorporation of PEG200 8 phr into PSi/NR would lead to the decreased in storage modulus whereas PEG1000 did not affect the modulus. It is important to note here that the content of PEG at 8 phr is thought to be excess. The excess PEG200 would then lead to lubricating effect. In the case of PEG1000, at T_g of NR, PEG1000 is still in the solid state hence did not affect T_g of rubber except at high temperature. In the case of Si-gel/NR, addition of PEG effectively enhance the crosslinking of the rubber as clearly showed by the increased in storage modulus. However, the excess content of both PEG200 and PEG1000 will lead to soften of the vulcanizate. Thus the vulcanizate contains PEG200 possess lower storage modulus than that with PEG1000.

Figure 19. Storage modulus (E') of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 20 Loss modulus (E'') of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

As it has been known that the crosslink density in the rubber vulcanizate effect T_g of the rubber. The higher the crosslink density, the higher the T_g . This is because crosslink in the rubber can obstruct the mobility of NR chain due to the molecular chains were tied together. Thus in the case of silica filled NR vulcanizates, T_g of the rubber phase was increased. Considering in case of 15Si-gel/NR+PEG, interconnection between Si-gel-rubber-Si-gel cluster was obviously occurred, as shown in **Figure 23**. Therefore both crosslinking and inter-connection between Si-gel clusters can responsible for the increasing of T_g of the Si-gel/NR and Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates. Nonetheless, when modified the vulcanizates with high molecular weight of PEG, PEG could act as plasticizer in 15PSi/NR+PEG system. This consequently eases the mobility of the rubber chains and lower T_g could be found, as shown in **Figure 22**.

Figure 21 Tan delta of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates

Figure 22 Glass transition temperatures (T_g) of 15PSi/NR+PEG and 15Si-gel/NR+PEG vulcanizates.

Figure 23 Si-gel-rubber-Si-gel interconnected network of dried rubber silica gelled in-situ

4. Conclusion

From this study, it was found that the addition of PEG could act as an activator in vulcanization reaction of accelerator and sulfur in 15Si-gel/NR and 15PSi/NR by forming as buffer layer on the silica particles. And this would enhance the complex formation of accelerator and activator, i.e. zinc oxide, subsequently complex with sulfur. Then sulfur crosslink between rubber-sulfur-rubber can occur. The PEG that form buffer layer on the silica could also help the dispersion of the silica. Si-gel was found very well dispersed in NR matrix than PSi. Low molecular weight PEG such as PEG200-PEG400 can be used as activator. It was found that PEG200 could result in optimum vulcanizates properties. However, using PEG with low molecular weight mentioned could cause bleeding of PEG out to the surface of rubber at room temperature. The incorporation of PEG with high molecular weight, i.e. PEG1000, was then applied to use instead of low molecular weight PEG. It was shown that low polarity of PEG1000 compared to PEG200, lead to slightly lower in crosslink density than using PEG200. Using PEG1000 seems to result in vulcanizates with heat sensitive than using PEG200. In term of dynamic properties it was found that the incorporation of PEG1000 into the silica filled rubber could give better mechanical properties at sub ambient temperature.

5. References

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Table 1 Table 1: Cure characteristic properties of NR compounds

Formulae	Scorch Time (m:s)	Cure Time (m:s)	Minimum Torque (N-m)	Maximum Torque (N-m)	Different Torque (N-m)
15PSi/NR	1:04	3:11	0.50	1.78	1.31
15PSi/NR+PEG200	0:27	2:43	0.64	3.89	3.25
15PSi/NR+PEG300	0:28	2:35	0.62	3.70	3.09
15PSi/NR+PEG400	0:33	2:26	0.42	3.34	2.92
15Si-gel/NR	8:07	19:14	0.88	1.39	0.52
15Si-gel/NR+PEG200	1:17	8:05	0.12	2.21	1.09
15Si-gel/NR+PEG300	1:18	8:16	1.08	2.18	1.11
15Si-gel/NR+PEG400	1:18	8:01	1.16	2.27	1.10

Table 2 Cure characteristic properties of PSi/NR and Si-gel/NR compounds

Formulae	Scorch time; ts (m:s)	Cure time; tc (m:s)	Minimum torque; ML (N-m)	Maximum torque; MH (N-m)	Different torque; Δs (N-m)
15PSi/NR	1:04	3:11	0.50	1.78	1.31
15PSi/NR+PEG200	0:29	2:07	0.32	3.32	3.00
15PSi/NR+PEG1000	0:34	2:24	0.49	2.91	2.41
15Si-gel/NR	8:07	19:14	0.88	1.39	0.52
15Si-gel/NR+PEG200	0:31	2:32	0.75	4.01	3.23
15Si-gel/NR+PEG1000	0:43	3:56	1.08	3.18	2.08